

1 THE CORRELATION OF SUBSTITUTION EFFECTS ACROSS POPULATIONS AND GENERATIONS IN
2 THE PRESENCE OF NON-ADDITIVE FUNCTIONAL GENE ACTION

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27 ABSTRACT

28

29 Allele substitution effects at quantitative trait loci (QTL) are part of the basis of quantitative
30 genetics theory and applications such as association analysis and genomic prediction. In
31 presence of non-additive functional gene action, substitution effects are not constant across
32 populations. We develop an original approach to model the difference in substitution effects
33 across populations as first order Taylor series expansion from a “focal” population. This
34 expansion involves the difference in allele frequencies and second-order statistical effects
35 (additive by additive and dominance). The change in allele frequencies is a function of
36 relationships (or genetic distances) across populations. As a result, it is possible to estimate
37 the correlation of substitution effects across two populations using three elements:
38 magnitudes of additive, dominance and additive by additive variance; relationships across
39 populations (similar to F_{st} indexes); and functions of heterozygosities at the markers.
40 Similarly, the theory applies as well to distinct generations in a population, in which case the
41 distance across generations is a function of increase of inbreeding. Using published
42 estimates of the needed parameters, we estimate the correlation between substitution
43 effects to be around 0.60 for distinct breeds and higher than 0.9 for generations closer than
44 5. Simulation results confirmed our derivations although our estimators tended to
45 underestimate the correlation. Our derivations are useful to understand the difficulty in
46 predicting across populations, to forecast the possibility of prediction across populations,
47 and we suggest that they can be useful to disentangle genotype by environment interaction
48 from genotype by genotype interaction.

49

INTRODUCTION

50

51

52 One of the aims of quantitative genetics is to provide methods for prediction, for instance
53 genomic prediction (prediction of livestock breeding values or of crop performance) or
54 polygenic risk score (risk of a disease in humans). These predictions would ideally work
55 across a range of populations (different breeds, future generations). Ideally, the prediction
56 goes through a process of identifying causal genes, estimating their effects in some
57 population, and transposing these effects to newly genotyped individuals (Lande and
58 Thompson 1990; Meuwissen *et al.* 2001). These “gene effects” are substitution effects –
59 loosely speaking, the regression of the own phenotype (for polygenic risk scores) or
60 expected progeny phenotypes (for estimated breeding values) on gene content at the locus.
61 Being able to use substitution effects at causal genes across populations and generations is
62 the ultimate goal of genomic prediction, QTL detection and to some extent of molecular
63 biology description of gene effects.

64

65 There are several obstacles for these aims. Finding and validating causal genes and
66 understanding their functional mechanism is extremely difficult (Grobet *et al.* 1997; Bonifati
67 *et al.* 2003; Rupp *et al.* 2015). In practice, predictions are done using SNP markers using
68 statistical genetics techniques. Use of markers results in very good predictions within
69 population but mediocre (at best) predictions across populations, even with very
70 sophisticated techniques (Hayes *et al.* 2009; Karoui *et al.* 2012; Porto-Neto *et al.* 2015;
71 MacLeod *et al.* 2016). Indeed, livestock and human genetics empirical results show
72 decreasing predictive ability with increasing genetic distance across distinct populations or
73 generations (Liu *et al.* 2016; Martin *et al.* 2019). The lack of perfect linkage disequilibrium

74 across markers and genes has been claimed to be a reason for this decrease in accuracy.
75 Adding extra information (more dense maps, biological prior information) should result in a
76 better choice of markers close to causal genes, and therefore in boosting predictive abilities
77 across populations (Roos *et al.* 2009; MacLeod *et al.* 2016). However, in practice, the
78 increase in predictive ability across populations is small at best (MacLeod *et al.* 2016;
79 Moghaddar *et al.* 2019). This is against results in simulations (Roos *et al.* 2009; MacLeod *et*
80 *al.* 2016) – but a problem in simulations is that typically gene effects are assumed to be
81 biologically additive and therefore constant across populations.

82

83 In fact, substitution (statistical) additive gene action is not homogeneous across populations,
84 even for exactly the same mutation. Examples in livestock genetics include myostatin gene
85 (Aiello *et al.* 2018) or DGAT1 (Gautier *et al.* 2007). Although part of these differences may be
86 due to genotype by environment interactions, it is also plausible that this is due to epistasis
87 or dominance; for instance this is the case in DGAT1 (Streit *et al.* 2011). For instance, in the
88 5-loci epistatic network in Carlborg *et al.* (2006) some substitution effects at genes switch
89 signs depending on genetic background. In *Drosophila*, estimated (GWAS) substitution
90 effects switched signs depended on the genetic background (Magwire *et al.* 2010; Mackay
91 2015).

92

93 There is indeed widespread evidence of biological epistasis (Mackay 2014). Whereas
94 biological epistasis does not impede (on the contrary) large additive variation (Hill *et al.*
95 2008; Mackay 2014; Mäki-Tanila and Hill 2014), it implies is that substitution effects do vary
96 across genetic backgrounds. Thus, in the presence of functional dominance and epistasis,
97 there is no stability of substitution effects across different genetic backgrounds. Even if in all

98 of these populations, additive variation accounts for most genetic variation, and additive
99 substitution effects are sizable (Hill *et al.* 2008), substitution effects may differ across
100 populations.

101

102 Recent simulations (Dai *et al.* 2020; Duenk *et al.* 2020) showed that the difference in
103 substitution effects across populations may be quite large under non-additive biological
104 gene action and increases with divergence of populations. It is relatively easy to derive
105 algebraic expressions for substitution effects α assuming specific hypothesis of biological
106 gene action. For instance, assuming biological additive and dominance effects only (Falconer
107 and Mackay 1996) results in $\alpha = a + (q - p)d$, whereas assuming additive, dominance and
108 additive by additive biological gene effects results in $\alpha_1 = a_1 + (q_1 + p_1)d_1 + (p_2 -$
109 $q_2)[aa]_{12}$ (Fuerst *et al.* 1997). Both of the approaches (simulation or analytical) are limited
110 because the hypotheses of specific biological gene actions (*e.g.* 2-loci interaction but not 3-
111 loci interaction) are too restrictive. Classically, these hypotheses are bypassed in quantitative
112 genetics by working on statistical effects (Falconer and Mackay 1996; Lynch and Walsh 1998;
113 Mäki-Tanila and Hill 2014).

114

115 The key parameter to describe the resemblance of statistical effects across populations is
116 the correlation of substitution effects across populations. Under certain assumptions
117 (independence of allele frequencies and substitution effects, appropriate coding; (Wientjes
118 *et al.* 2017)), this correlation can be estimated from SNP markers and data of two
119 populations (Karoui *et al.* 2012; Wientjes *et al.* 2017), and can easily be accommodated into
120 genomic prediction models (Karoui *et al.* 2012; Xiang *et al.* 2017). In addition to empirical
121 results, some theory to describe the resemblance of substitution effects across different

122 populations would be helpful to (1) better understand and quantify the change in *true*
123 substitution effects (*i.e.* if true genes instead of markers were being used), (2) give upper
124 bounds for genomic prediction across populations/generations, and (3) allow *a priori*
125 planning of genomic predictions *i.e.* including or not different subpopulations.

126

127 The aim of this work is to develop a theory to predict the extent of change of substitution
128 effects across space (breeds, lines) and across time (generations), without invoking or
129 assuming specific modes of biological gene action. We obtain explicit estimators that are
130 functions of additive, dominance and additive by additive variances, genetic distances across
131 populations, and distributions of allele frequencies. We check and illustrate our theory using
132 published results and simulations considering dominance and epistasis (additive by additive
133 and complementary) from 5-loci interactions.

134

135 MATERIALS AND METHODS

136

137 **Theory**

138

139 **General Theory.** Here, we model difference of substitution effects across populations as
140 Taylor expansions around a “focal” population. Using Kojima’s method (Kojima 1959, 1961),
141 we put additive substitution effects as a function of differences in allele frequencies across
142 populations, “focal” additive substitution effects, and higher order (dominance, additive by
143 additive epistasis) statistical effects. From here, we show that the correlation of substitution
144 effects across populations is a function of their relationship (or genetic distance), the
145 additive, dominant and additive by additive genetic variances, the average heterozygosities

146 and average squared heterozygosities. All these parameters can be estimated in real
147 populations. In the following, we try to stick to Mäki-Tanila and Hill (2014) notation. Many
148 details are given as Appendix in the Supplementary Material.

149

150 Note that our procedure is general – it does not invoke neither any particular mechanism for
151 epistasis or dominance, nor knowledge of individual QTL effects and locations. We assume
152 that the population mean is a (possibly complex) function of QTL allele frequencies \mathbf{p} and
153 QTL functional or biological effects. The latter, albeit unknown, are assumed to be constant
154 across populations - we therefore assume no genotype by environment interactions.

155

156 Consider the correlation $r(\alpha_i^b, \alpha_i^{b'})$ of substitution effects $\alpha^{(b)}$ and $\alpha^{(b')}$ across respective
157 populations (breeds, heterotic groups, lines, or generations) b and b' . It is known that, in
158 presence of dominant and epistatic biological interactions, the value of α depends on the
159 allele frequencies and biological effects; for instance, $\alpha_1 = a_1 + (q_1 + p_1)d_1 +$
160 $(p_2 - q_2)[aa]_{12}$ for 2-locus epistasis (Fuerst *et al.* 1997), for $p_1 = 1 - q_1$ and $p_2 = 1 - q_2$
161 frequencies at loci 1 and 2, respectively. Inspired by this, we want to write the correlation
162 $r(\alpha_i^b, \alpha_i^{b'})$ for a locus i as a function of respective allele frequencies, \mathbf{p}^b and $\mathbf{p}^{b'}$, but in a
163 general manner, without defining a particular functional or biological gene action. We use a
164 first order Taylor series expansion to approximate additive substitution effects in a
165 population b and in population b' , as a function of effects in another “focal” population (that
166 we call “0”) and the differences in allelic frequencies across the three populations. By doing
167 this, it can be shown that the difference of substitution effects between two populations is
168 (approximately) a function of the genetic distance of the two populations to the focal

169 population, and the magnitude of dominance and second order epistatic variances in the
170 focal population.

171

172

173 To derive additive substitution effects α as function of allelic frequencies \mathbf{p} , we use Kojima's
174 definition of statistical effects as first, second... derivatives of the mean of the population (μ)
175 as a function of p . We don't invoke any explicit function – we just presume that there is
176 one, in other words, change in allele frequencies of the population implies change in the
177 total average genotypic value. Using Kojima's method, the additive substitution effect at the
178 i -th locus is the first derivative (Kojima 1959, 1961):

$$\alpha_i = \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial \mu}{\partial p_i}$$

179

180 Higher order effects implying locus i are higher order derivatives of μ but we remark that
181 they can equally be obtained as derivatives of α_i . The dominance deviation at the i -th locus
182 (that we denote as d^* to distinguish from the biological or functional effect d (Falconer and
183 Mackay 1996)) is:

$$d_i^* = -\frac{1}{4} \frac{\partial^2 \mu}{\partial p_i^2} = -\frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial \alpha_i}{\partial p_i}$$

184

185 The negative sign comes because the dominance deviation is usually understood as a feature
186 of *heterozygosity*, in other words, it is of opposite sign than the increase of homozygosity in
187 ∂p_i^2 . Last, the epistatic pairwise deviation of locus i with j is

$$(\alpha\alpha)_{ij} = \frac{1}{4} \frac{\partial^2 \mu}{\partial p_i \partial p_j} = \frac{1}{2} \frac{\partial \alpha_i}{\partial p_j}$$

188

189 This is positive because it is the effect of increasing both p_i and p_j .

190

191 Kojima's method shows, therefore, that higher order effects of one locus are derivatives of

192 lower order effects. With these elements we can make a Taylor order expansion of

193 α_i around frequencies in the focal population, \mathbf{p}_0 , so that $\mathbf{p} = \mathbf{p}_0 + \boldsymbol{\epsilon}$, such that we create a

194 function $\alpha_i(\mathbf{p})$. A meaningful value for \mathbf{p}_0 is a "focal" population for which there are

195 estimates of additive, dominance and second order epistatic variances. In the Appendix, we

196 show that the Taylor linear approximation of the substitution effects α_i^b and $\alpha_i^{b'}$ for two

197 populations b and b' is:

$$\alpha_i^b \approx \alpha_i^0 + 2\epsilon_i^b(-d_i^{*0}) + 2\boldsymbol{\epsilon}^{(b)'}(\boldsymbol{\alpha}\boldsymbol{\alpha})_i^0 \quad (1)$$

$$\alpha_i^{b'} \approx \alpha_i^0 + 2\epsilon_i^{b'}(-d_i^{*0}) + 2\boldsymbol{\epsilon}^{(b')'}(\boldsymbol{\alpha}\boldsymbol{\alpha})_i^0$$

198

199 where we use differences in allele frequencies from the focal population, $\boldsymbol{\epsilon}^{(b)} = \mathbf{p}^{(b)} - \mathbf{p}_0$

200 and $\boldsymbol{\epsilon}^{(b')} = \mathbf{p}^{(b')} - \mathbf{p}_0$, d_i^{*0} is the statistical dominance deviation at the locus i and $(\boldsymbol{\alpha}\boldsymbol{\alpha})_i^0$ is

201 a vector containing epistatic substitution effects of locus i with the rest of loci.

202

203 From equation 1, the covariance across two populations b and b' of the two substitution

204 effects α_i^b and $\alpha_i^{b'}$ of the locus i is a function of the covariance of $\boldsymbol{\epsilon}^{(b)}$ and $\boldsymbol{\epsilon}^{(b')}$ and is:

$$\text{Cov}(\alpha_i^{(b)}, \alpha_i^{(b')}) \quad (2)$$

$$\begin{aligned} &= \text{Cov}(\alpha_i^0 + 2\epsilon_i^{(b)}(-d_i^{*0}) + 2\epsilon^{(b)'}(\alpha\alpha)_i^0, \alpha_i^0 \\ &+ 2\epsilon_i^{(b')}(-d_i^{*0}) + 2\epsilon^{(b')'}(\alpha\alpha)_i^0) \\ &= \text{Var}(\alpha_i^0) + 4\text{Cov}(\epsilon_i^{(b)}, \epsilon_i^{(b')})\text{Var}(d_i^{*0}) \\ &+ 4\text{tr}\left(\text{Cov}(\epsilon^{(b)}, \epsilon^{(b')}')\text{Var}((\alpha\alpha)_i^0)\right) \end{aligned}$$

205

206 Where $\text{Cov}(\epsilon^{(b)}, \epsilon^{(b')'})$ and $\text{Var}((\alpha\alpha)_i^0)$ are matrices. Note that we can drop terms
 207 including e.g. $\text{Cov}(\alpha^0, (\alpha\alpha)_i^0)$ as the different statistical effects (additive dominant,
 208 epistatic) are mutually orthogonal. Also, we assume $\epsilon^{(b)}$ (change in allele frequencies) and
 209 the different effects d_i^{*0} and $(\alpha\alpha)_i^0$ to be independent. The equation 2 has different terms
 210 that are briefly presented here; more details are in the Appendix.

211

212 The variance of statistical additive, dominant and additive by additive effects are (Mäki-
 213 Tanila and Hill 2014):

$$\text{Var}(\alpha_i^0) = \sigma_\alpha^{(0)2} = \frac{\sigma_A^2}{n\bar{H}}$$

$$\text{Var}(d^{*0}) = \sigma_d^{(0)2} = \frac{\sigma_D^2}{n\bar{H}^2}$$

$$\text{Var}((\alpha\alpha)_{i,j,j>i}^0) = \sigma_{(\alpha\alpha)}^{(0)2} = \frac{\sigma_{AA}^2}{0.5n(n-1)\bar{H}\bar{H}} \approx 4 \frac{\sigma_{AA}^2}{n^2\bar{H}\bar{H}}$$

$$\text{Var}((\alpha\alpha)_i^0) = \mathbf{I} \otimes \sigma_{(\alpha\alpha)}^{(0)2} \approx 4\mathbf{I} \frac{\sigma_{AA}^2}{n^2\bar{H}\bar{H}}$$

214 for n the number of QTL loci and using functions of heterozygosities:

$$\bar{H} = E(2p_i(1-p_i))$$

$$\overline{H^2} = E(4p_i(1-p_i)p_i(1-p_i))$$

$$\overline{HH} = E_{i>j} (2p_i(1-p_i)2p_j(1-p_j)) \approx \frac{1}{2}\overline{HH}$$

215

216 All variances and effects refer to a focal population (with sub/superindex “0”) with allele
 217 frequencies p^0 and effects α^0 . Note that we assume HWE and LE. Of course, we don’t know
 218 allele frequencies or even numbers of true causal genes, but the first can be prudently
 219 guessed and the later cancel out in the following.

220

221 A relationship coefficient across populations b and b' is $\gamma_{b,b'} = 8Cov(p_i^{(b)}, p_i^{(b')})$; also,
 222 $\gamma_{b,b'} = -4D^2$ where D^2 is the average square of the Euclidean distance (Robertson 1975;
 223 Bonhomme *et al.* 2010; Garcia-Baccino *et al.* 2017). Similarly, we introduce a measure of
 224 similarity $\gamma_{b,b'}^\epsilon$ (more details in the Appendix) such that

$$Cov(\epsilon_i^{(b)}, \epsilon_i^{(b')}) = \frac{1}{8}\gamma_{b,b'}^\epsilon = \frac{1}{8}(\gamma_{b,b'} - \gamma_{b,0} - \gamma_{b',0} + \gamma_{0,0})$$

225 This is the remaining similarity of b and b' once similarity of both to “0” has been discounted
 226 If the focal (“0”) population is population b , then $Cov(\epsilon_i^{(b')}, \epsilon_i^{(b')}) = Var(\epsilon_i^{(b')}) =$
 227 $\frac{1}{8}(\gamma_{b'} + \gamma_b - 2\gamma_{b,b'})$. In fact, in this case $Cov(\epsilon_i^{(b')}, \epsilon_i^{(b')}) = \frac{1}{8}(\gamma_{b'} + \gamma_b - 2\gamma_{b,b'})$ is
 228 proportional to the F_{st} differentiation index across b and b' such that the pairwise

229 $F_{st} = \frac{\frac{1}{8}(\gamma_{b'} + \gamma_b - 2\gamma_{b,b'})}{1 - \frac{1}{8}(\gamma_{b'} + \gamma_b + 2\gamma_{b,b'})}$. This is obtained from the definition of F_{st} from average

230 relationships within and across populations (Caballero and Toro 2002; Caballero 2020) as
 231 detailed in the Supplementary Material. The main difference between the F_{st} and our
 232 relationship coefficients γ resides in the fact that F_{st} describes divergence, and is relative to
 233 the set of populations being considered, whereas γ coefficients describe similarity, and are

234 not relative to any particular set of populations; for instance, they can be defined and
 235 obtained for pairs of populations, to be later combined. Across all loci, $Cov(\epsilon^{(b)}, \epsilon^{(b')'}) =$
 236 $I \frac{1}{8} \gamma_{b,b'}^\epsilon$. Thus, the covariance of changes in allele frequencies is a function of relatedness
 237 across populations or, equivalently, of their differentiation.

238

239 The term including $Cov(\epsilon^{(b)}(\alpha\alpha)_i^0, \epsilon^{(b')}(\alpha\alpha)_i^0)$ uses the covariance of quadratic forms
 240 (Searle 1971) (eq. 58) and is detailed in the Appendix. It assumes uncorrelated $\epsilon^{(b)}$ and
 241 $(\alpha\alpha)_i^0$, and normality for both. It is customary in population genetics to assume normality
 242 for small changes in allele frequencies (Lewontin and Krakauer 1973; Bonhomme *et al.*
 243 2010).

244

245 Combining expressions above, equation (2) becomes

$$\begin{aligned}
 Cov(\alpha_i^b, \alpha_i^{b'}) &= Var(\alpha_i^0) + 4Cov(\epsilon_i^{(b)}, \epsilon_i^{(b')'}) Var(d_i^{*0}) & (3) \\
 &+ 4tr\left(Cov(\epsilon^{(b)}, \epsilon^{(b')'}) Var((\alpha\alpha)_i^0)\right) \\
 &= \frac{\sigma_A^2}{n\bar{H}} + 4 \frac{\gamma_{b,b'}^\epsilon}{8} \frac{\sigma_D^2}{nH^2} + 4n \frac{\gamma_{b,b'}^\epsilon}{8} 4 \frac{\sigma_{AA}^2}{n^2\bar{H}\bar{H}} \\
 &= \frac{\sigma_A^2}{n\bar{H}} + \frac{1}{2} \gamma_{b,b'}^\epsilon \frac{\sigma_D^2}{nH^2} + 2\gamma_{b,b'}^\epsilon \frac{\sigma_{AA}^2}{n\bar{H}\bar{H}} \\
 &= \frac{1}{n} \left(\frac{\sigma_A^2}{\bar{H}} + \frac{1}{2} \gamma_{b,b'}^\epsilon \frac{\sigma_D^2}{H^2} + 2\gamma_{b,b'}^\epsilon \frac{\sigma_{AA}^2}{\bar{H}\bar{H}} \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

246

247 The quantities involved in Equation 3 are (1) the covariance in change of allelic frequencies ϵ
 248 in b and b' (called $\gamma_{b,b'}^\epsilon$), which describes the similarity of populations b and b' using the
 249 focal population as a reference, and (2) the variance of statistical additive, dominant and

250 additive by additive effects. We have used $4tr\left(Cov\left(\epsilon^{(b)}, \epsilon^{(b')}\right)Var\left((\alpha\alpha)_i^0\right)\right) =$

$$251 \quad 4tr\left(\left(I\frac{1}{8}\gamma_{b,b'}^\epsilon\right)\left(4I\frac{\sigma_{AA}^2}{n^2\bar{H}\bar{H}}\right)\right) = 4n\left(\left(\frac{1}{8}\gamma_{b,b'}^\epsilon\right)\left(4\frac{\sigma_{AA}^2}{n^2\bar{H}\bar{H}}\right)\right) = 2\gamma_{b,b'}^\epsilon\frac{\sigma_{AA}^2}{n\bar{H}\bar{H}}$$

252

253 Whereas

$$Var(\alpha_i^b) = \frac{1}{n}\left(\frac{\sigma_A^2}{\bar{H}} + \frac{1}{2}\gamma_b^\epsilon\frac{\sigma_D^2}{\bar{H}^2} + 2\gamma_b^\epsilon\frac{\sigma_{AA}^2}{\bar{H}\bar{H}}\right)$$

254 From here the correlation of α across populations is (factorizing out $\frac{1}{n}$)

$$r(\alpha_i^b, \alpha_i^{b'}) = \tag{4}$$

$$\frac{\frac{\sigma_A^2}{\bar{H}} + \frac{1}{2}\gamma_{b,b'}^\epsilon\frac{\sigma_D^2}{\bar{H}^2} + 2\gamma_{b,b'}^\epsilon\frac{\sigma_{AA}^2}{\bar{H}\bar{H}}}{\sqrt{\left(\frac{\sigma_A^2}{\bar{H}} + \frac{1}{2}\gamma_b^\epsilon\frac{\sigma_D^2}{\bar{H}^2} + 2\gamma_b^\epsilon\frac{\sigma_{AA}^2}{\bar{H}\bar{H}}\right)\left(\frac{\sigma_A^2}{\bar{H}} + \frac{1}{2}\gamma_{b'}^\epsilon\frac{\sigma_D^2}{\bar{H}^2} + 2\gamma_{b'}^\epsilon\frac{\sigma_{AA}^2}{\bar{H}\bar{H}}\right)}}$$

255

256 It can already be seen that $\frac{\sigma_A^2}{\bar{H}}$ is both on the numerator and denominator. If the focal

257 population is population b , then $\gamma_b^\epsilon = \gamma_{b,b'}^\epsilon = 0$, but $\gamma_{b'}^\epsilon = (\gamma_{b'} + \gamma_b - 2\gamma_{b,b'})$ (as an aside,

258 this is positive, which results in the correlation $r(\alpha_i^b, \alpha_i^{b'})$ being positive), and Equation 4

259 becomes

$$r(\alpha_i^b, \alpha_i^{b'}) = \frac{\frac{\sigma_A^2}{\bar{H}}}{\sqrt{\frac{\sigma_A^2}{\bar{H}}\left(\frac{\sigma_A^2}{\bar{H}} + \frac{1}{2}\gamma_{b'}^\epsilon\frac{\sigma_D^2}{\bar{H}^2} + 2\gamma_{b'}^\epsilon\frac{\sigma_{AA}^2}{\bar{H}\bar{H}}\right)}} = \frac{\sqrt{\frac{\sigma_A^2}{\bar{H}}}}{\sqrt{\frac{\sigma_A^2}{\bar{H}} + \frac{1}{2}\gamma_{b'}^\epsilon\frac{\sigma_D^2}{\bar{H}^2} + 2\gamma_{b'}^\epsilon\frac{\sigma_{AA}^2}{\bar{H}\bar{H}}}}$$

260

261 Factorizing out \bar{H} we arrive to the slightly clearer expression

$$\begin{aligned}
r(\alpha_i^b, \alpha_i^{b'}) &= \frac{\sqrt{\sigma_A^2}}{\sqrt{\sigma_A^2 + \gamma_{b'}^\epsilon \left(\frac{1}{2} \frac{\bar{H}}{H^2} \sigma_D^2 + 2 \frac{\sigma_{AA}^2}{\bar{H}} \right)}} \quad (5) \\
&= \frac{\sqrt{\sigma_A^2}}{\sqrt{\sigma_A^2 + (\gamma_{b'} + \gamma_b - 2\gamma_{b,b'}) \left(\frac{1}{2} \frac{\bar{H}}{H^2} \sigma_D^2 + 2 \frac{\sigma_{AA}^2}{\bar{H}} \right)}}
\end{aligned}$$

262 which shows well that the correlation is a function of relationships across populations
263 $(\gamma_{b'} + \gamma_b - 2\gamma_{b,b'})$ and weights of additive vs. non-additive variances.

264

265 Finally, our expression for $r(\alpha_i^b, \alpha_i^{b'})$ includes values for the three main genetic variances
266 (which can be estimated from data), measures of genetic distances (which can be estimated
267 from data) and “good guesses” of the distribution of QTL effects – the latter can come either
268 via markers (sequence or chip SNP) or guesses (*i.e.*, U-shaped, flat, etc.).

269

270 Thus, the algorithm to estimate *a priori* the correlation of α across populations b and b' ,
271 $r(\alpha_i^b, \alpha_i^{b'})$, is:

- 272 1. Define a focal population with existing estimates of statistical additive, dominance,
273 and additive by additive variances (this focal population can actually be population b
274 or b')
- 275 2. Compute average heterozygosity \bar{H} and average squared heterozygosity $\overline{H^2}$ in the
276 focal population, either from markers or from guesses.
- 277 3. Using markers, compute relationships γ within and across the three populations

278 4. Apply equation 4. If the focal population is population b or b' , apply the equivalent
279 Equation 5.

280

281 **Covariance across generations within one breed.** The definition above of two populations is
282 general enough that we can consider any two populations, *e.g.* two breeds (Angus and
283 Hereford), two strains (New Zealand Holstein and US Holstein) or two generations or time
284 frames (*e.g.* animals born in 2000 vs. animals born in 2005, or animals born in 2000 vs. their
285 descendants). There is evidence that across-generations genetic correlation decreases with
286 time to values as low as 0.6 (Tsuruta *et al.* 2004; Haile-Mariam and Pryce 2015). As explained
287 before, the across-generation genetic correlation does not depend only on the across-breed
288 correlation of substitution effects, first because allele frequencies and substitution effects
289 might be correlated due to selection, second because of genotype by environment
290 interactions. Anyway, part of the across-generation genetic correlation can be accounted for
291 by our model, based on the evolution of average coancestry in the breed.

292

293 We will talk about “generations” but ideas apply to pedigrees with overlapping generations
294 as well. Consider that we called populations b and b' are animals born at time t_1 and t_2 , with
295 $t_2 > t_1$. Allele frequencies at generation t are (for a single locus) $p_t = \frac{1}{2n_t} \mathbf{1}'\mathbf{z}$ where \mathbf{z} has
296 gene content in the form $\{0,1,2\}$. The variance of p_t is $Var(p_t) = \frac{1}{4} \bar{A}_t 2pq = \frac{pq}{2} \bar{A}_t$ (because
297 $Var(\mathbf{z}) = \mathbf{A}_t 2pq$), where \mathbf{A} is the pedigree-based relationship matrix and \mathbf{A}_t the submatrix
298 corresponding to animals born at time t . Considering $\mathbf{A}^{(\gamma)}$ build with metafounders (Legarra
299 *et al.* 2015) then $Var(p_t) = \bar{A}_t^{(\gamma)} / 8$. Note that if there is a single metafounder then
300 $\mathbf{A}^{(\gamma)} = \mathbf{A} \left(1 - \frac{\gamma}{2}\right) + \mathbf{1}\mathbf{1}'\gamma$. The covariance between two generations is, similarly,

301 $Cov(p_{t_1}, p_{t_2}) = \bar{A}_{t_1, t_2}^{(\gamma)}/8$, so here $\bar{A}_{t_1, t_2}^{(\gamma)}$ takes the role of the $\gamma_{b, b'}$ before. Leading to, if we
 302 take t_1 as the focal population,

$$Cov(\epsilon_i^{(t_2)}, \epsilon_i^{(t_1)}) = \frac{1}{8} (\bar{A}_{t_2}^{(\gamma)} + \bar{A}_{t_1}^{(\gamma)} - 2\bar{A}_{t_1, t_2}^{(\gamma)})$$

303 This involves average relationships within and across generations. From here, the
 304 correlation of substitution effects across t_1 and t_2 is

$$r(\alpha_i^{t_2}, \alpha_i^{t_1}) = \frac{\sqrt{\sigma_A^2}}{\sqrt{\sigma_A^2 + (\bar{A}_{(\gamma)t_2} + \bar{A}_{(\gamma)t_1} - 2\bar{A}_{(\gamma)t_1, t_2}) \left(\frac{1}{2} \frac{\bar{H}}{H^2} \sigma_D^2 + 2 \frac{\sigma_{AA}^2}{H} \right)}} \quad (6)$$

305
 306 Thus, the correlation of substitution effects decreases when there is large drift: high average
 307 relationships within each generation combined with low relationship across. This is the case
 308 for instance if parents of the next generation are very highly selected without restrictions in
 309 future inbreeding, resulting in a considerable change in allele frequencies over the
 310 generations.

311
 312 Values of $(\bar{A}_{(\gamma)t_2} + \bar{A}_{(\gamma)t_1} - 2\bar{A}_{(\gamma)t_1, t_2})$ can be easily computed, even for large pedigrees,
 313 using Colleau (2002). This can be approximated (see Appendix) as $\bar{A}_{(\gamma)t_2} + \bar{A}_{(\gamma)t_1} -$
 314 $2\bar{A}_{(\gamma)t_1, t_2} \approx (t_2 - t_1)\Delta F_{(\gamma)}$ for small values of $\Delta F_{(\gamma)}$ and steady increase of inbreeding. Note
 315 that $\Delta F_{(\gamma)} = \left(1 - \frac{\gamma}{2}\right) \Delta F$ as $\mathbf{A}_{(\gamma)} = \mathbf{A} \left(1 - \frac{\gamma}{2}\right) + \mathbf{1}\mathbf{1}'\gamma$. This agrees with classical theory
 316 (Falconer and Mackay 1996): the variance in change of allele frequencies from one
 317 generation to the next is simply ΔF . Typical values of ΔF in livestock (rabbits, pigs, cattle or
 318 sheep) are at most 0.01 per generation (Welsh *et al.* 2010; García-Ruiz *et al.* 2016; E. N.

319 Fernandez, J.P. Sanchez, R. Martinez, A. Legarra, M. Baselga 2017; Rodríguez-Ramilo *et al.*
320 2019), although this is potentially changing with genomic selection. Substituting in Equation
321 6 we obtain the correlation of substitution effects as a function of increase in inbreeding:

$$r(\alpha_i^{t_2}, \alpha_i^{t_1}) = \frac{\sqrt{\sigma_A^2}}{\sqrt{\sigma_A^2 + \Delta F_{(y)} \left(\frac{1}{2} \frac{\bar{H}}{H^2} \sigma_D^2 + 2 \frac{\sigma_{AA}^2}{H} \right)}} \quad (7)$$

322

323

324

325 **Examples**

326

327 **Estimates of correlation across populations using literature values.** From values of the
 328 literature, the previous expressions, equations (5) and (7) were applied to obtain guesses of
 329 the correlation of substitution effects across different populations and generations within
 330 population. Estimates of statistical non-additive variation are scarce, as are estimates of
 331 distances across populations in terms of covariance of allele frequencies. Table 1 shows two
 332 pairs of populations in pigs (Xiang *et al.* 2016) and cattle (VanRaden *et al.* 2011; Legarra *et*
 333 *al.* 2015), and the corresponding relationships expressed as $\gamma_{b,b'} = 8Cov(p^b, p^{b'})$. In all
 334 cases, the reference allele has been randomized so $E(p) = 0.5$.

335

336 Table 1. Relationships within and across two pairs of populations

		Holstein	Jersey
Cattle	Holstein	0.55	0.48
	Jersey	0.48	0.77
		Landrace	Yorkshire
Pigs	Landrace	0.76	0.26
	Yorkshire	0.26	0.73

337 Estimates from cattle (VanRaden *et al.* 2011; Legarra *et al.* 2015) and pigs (Xiang *et al.* 2016).

338

339 Table 2 includes estimates for additive, dominance and epistatic variation iWe used
 340 estimates for milk yield in Simmenthal cattle (Fuerst and Sölkner 1994) as if it was Holstein,

341 and for litter size in a commercial pig line (Vitezica *et al.* 2018) as if it was Landrace, because
 342 we could not find estimates in the same populations.

343

344 Table 2. Variance component estimates, as ratio from phenotypic variance, from literature

Species	σ_A^2	σ_D^2	σ_{AA}^2
Cattle	0.20	0.09	0.15
Pigs	0.092	0.020	0.016

345 Estimates for milk yield in cattle (Fuerst and Sölkner 1994) and litter size in pigs (Vitezica *et*
 346 *al.* 2018).

347

348 Then, we assumed three distributions for allele frequencies, following Hill *et al.* (2008): a
 349 uniform distribution (“Uniform”), a U-shaped distributions with $f(p) \propto p^{-1}(1-p)^{-1}$ with
 350 effective population size of 50 (“Hill”). We also assumed a Beta(0.04, 0.04) distribution,
 351 which is an extreme U-shaped distribution (“Extreme”) in which roughly 80% of the QTLs
 352 have minor allele frequency lower than 0.01. This results in respective values of $\bar{H} =$
 353 $(0.333, 0.107, 0.037)$ and $\overline{H^2} = (0.133, 0.018, 0.013)$. Using the values described above, we
 354 estimated the correlation of QTL effects across breeds, $r(\alpha_i^b, \alpha_i^{b'})$, using equation (5).

355

356 Similarly, the correlation of QTL effects a certain number of generations away, $r(\alpha_i^{t_2}, \alpha_i^{t_1})$,
 357 was obtained applying Equation (7). An increase $\Delta F = 0.01$ resulting in $\Delta F_\gamma = 0.01(1 -$
 358 $\gamma/2)$ per generation was assumed, for the same assumed variances and allele frequency
 359 distributions.

360

361 **Simulations.** The objective of the simulation is to verify our results considering different
362 kinds of non-additive biological gene action, and not to infer the values of the correlation of
363 substitution effects across populations as this requires realistic presumptions of the forms
364 and magnitudes of epistatic interactions, something that is largely unknown.

365

366 We simulated two divergent populations using QMSim (Sargolzaei and Schenkel 2009). First,
367 2000 generations of the historical population were generated with an effective population
368 size of 1500 individuals, followed by a gradual contraction during the following 500
369 generations to an effective population size of 100 individuals. It followed a gradual
370 expansion to a population size of 1500 during the last 500 generations. From this common
371 historical population, two divergent populations were selected in opposite directions for 5
372 generations of 1000 individuals each. Selection was for a trait with narrow-sense heritability
373 of 1, as a device to speed up divergence; however, for the purposes of this work we
374 simulated another, uncorrelated, trait (with a broad-sense heritability of 1). There were 30
375 chromosomes of 100 cM each and 66,000 segregating loci (60,000 SNPs and 6,000 QTLs) in
376 the first generation of the historical population. The number of segregating QTLs and SNPs in
377 the last generation of the historical population was 750 and 13,555, respectively.

378

379 To simulate non-additive biological gene action, we considered three scenarios: Complete
380 Dominance (within locus), 5 locus complementary epistasis and 5 locus additive by additive
381 epistasis. Complete dominance has the genotypic value of the heterozygote equal to one of
382 the homozygotes. Additive by additive epistasis can be understood as a pure multiplication
383 of gene contents. Complementary epistasis implies that a simultaneous homozygote
384 genotype at all loci results in a genotypic value, and any other combination in another

385 genotypic value. Explicit functional additive effects were not simulated. These scenarios are
386 similar to Hill *et al.* (2008) but instead of considering 2 loci we consider 5 (details are given in
387 the Appendix).

388

389 For epistasis, networks are internally epistatic but contribute additively to the total
390 phenotype. Loci within a network were picked up at random within chromosomes, resulting
391 in very low LD across loci within network. We considered 5 networks per chromosome
392 yielding a total of 150 networks. We derived substitution effects α algebraically for the three
393 different cases (details are given in the Appendix). We used those expressions to evaluate
394 the true substitution effects, and to obtain the true value $r(\alpha^b, \alpha^{b'})$. At the end, we had
395 two populations of 5000 individuals each (1000 individuals per generation). Using markers
396 (alternatively, QTL loci) and simulated phenotypes, we estimated (1) variance components
397 σ_A^2 , σ_D^2 and σ_{AA}^2 using G-REML (Vitezica *et al.* 2018) in population 1 (all 5 generations totaling
398 5000 animals). We then computed, using markers (alternatively, QTL loci), relationships γ
399 within and across populations and the functions of heterozygosities \bar{H} and $\overline{H^2}$. Then, using
400 Equation 4 we predicted $r(\alpha^b, \alpha^{b'})$ across populations 1 and 2 within generation 5, and we
401 predicted $r(\alpha^{t_1}, \alpha^{t_2})$ within population 1 for $t_1 = 1$ and $t_2 = 2 \dots 5$. The purpose of using,
402 alternatively to genotypes at markers, genotypes at QTL was to verify or discard that results
403 were due to imperfect Linkage Disequilibrium.

404

405 **Data Availability Statement.** Appendix associated with this manuscript is in Figshare. Code
406 and files for simulations can be found in
407 http://genoweb.toulouse.inra.fr/~alegarra/simulation_alpha.tar.gz . All other results can be
408 reproduced using equations and figures from the text.

409

410

RESULTS

411

412 **Estimates of correlation across populations using literature values.** The results for
413 reasonable guesses of the distribution of QTL substitution effects are in Table 3. The
414 correlation of QTL substitution effects across breeds were roughly 0.6 for the “Uniform”
415 distribution, whereas the “Extreme” distribution resulted in numbers close to 0.4. These
416 numbers agree reasonably well with scarce estimates of genetic correlation (although,
417 strictly speaking, not the same thing) in the literature: 0.4 to 0.8 for production traits (Karoui
418 *et al.* 2012), 0.3 to 0.5 for milk yield (Legarra *et al.* 2014) and 0.6 for body condition (Porto-
419 Neto *et al.* 2015). It may be argued that these studies used SNPs instead of true QTLs;
420 however, Wientjes *et al.* (Wientjes *et al.* 2017) in a simulation study obtained unbiased
421 estimates of correlation across QTLs using SNP markers for a true correlation of 0.5.

422

423 Table 3: Estimates of correlations of QTL effects across breeds based on values from Tables 1
424 and 2 and Equation 5, for different distributions of QTL frequencies

Species	Uniform	Hill ¹	Extreme ²
Cattle	0.60	0.39	0.25
Pigs	0.66	0.46	0.31
Maize	0.57	0.36	0.22

425 ¹ U-shaped distribution with effective population size of 50

426 ² Beta(0.04, 0.04) distribution

427

428 Concerning decrease of correlations across generations, results (Table 4) show a mild
 429 decrease, and this decrease is more sensitive to the assumed distribution of allelic
 430 frequencies than the previous ones concerning correlation across populations. There are no
 431 explicit estimates of genomic correlation across generations, but drops in the accuracy of
 432 genomic prediction have been reported (Wolc *et al.* 2011; Baloché *et al.* 2014; Liu *et al.*
 433 2016).

434

435

436 Table 4: Correlation of QTL effects across time, based on values from Table 1 and 2 and

437 Equation 7, for different distributions of QTL frequencies

Species	Distance in generations	Uniform	Hill ¹	Extreme ²
Cattle	1	0.98	0.95	0.88
	2	0.97	0.90	0.79
	5	0.92	0.80	0.63
	10	0.85	0.67	0.50
Pigs	1	1.00	0.99	0.97
	2	0.99	0.98	0.94
	5	0.98	0.94	0.88
	10	0.96	0.89	0.79

438 ¹ U-shaped distribution with effective population size of 50

439 ² Beta(0.04, 0.04) distribution

440

441 **Simulations.** Estimated variance components (expressed as ratios from total phenotypic
442 variance σ^2) with marker genotypes and with QTL genotypes are shown in Table 5. The part
443 of non-additive variance increases with the complexity of the system, although this is in part
444 because we chose on purpose very artificial examples. In general, the two estimates agree,
445 although with markers we estimate non-zero epistatic additive by additive variance in the
446 case of complete dominance, where it is zero. This is due to imperfect LD between QTL and
447 markers and LD across QTLs and also across markers (Campos *et al.* 2019). Indeed, when we
448 estimated variance components with QTLs, this epistatic variance disappeared as shown in
449 the bottom three rows of Table 5.

450

451

452 Table 5. Estimated Ratios of additive, dominance and additive by additive variances σ_A^2/σ^2 ,
 453 σ_D^2/σ^2 and σ_{AA}^2/σ^2 (standard errors) in population 1, estimated with markers (three top
 454 rows) and QTLs (three bottom rows)

	σ_A^2/σ^2	σ_D^2/σ^2	σ_{AA}^2/σ^2
Marker-based			
Complete	0.709 (0.017)	0.130 (0.011)	0.144 (0.031)
Dominance			
Complementary	0.440 (0.025)	0.144 (0.016)	0.309 (0.047)
Epistasis			
Additive by additive	0.232 (0.025)	0.040 (0.015)	0.587(0.053)
QTL-based			
Complete	0.676 (0.009)	0.324 (0.009)	0.00001(0.004)
Dominance			
Complementary	0.512 (0.019)	0.145 (0.011)	0.248 (0.022)
Epistasis			
Additive by additive	0.265 (0.020)	0.009 (0.006)	0.520(0.036)

455

456 Estimates of correlation across substitution effects are presented in Table 6 (across
 457 population) and 7 (within population). Our estimates tend to agree with true values, but they
 458 underestimate the true values. Still, they clearly tell apart one scenario with low correlation
 459 (i.e. additive by additive) from one with high correlation (i.e. complete dominance). Using
 460 QTL genotypes for estimation instead of markers yield similar results, so incomplete linkage
 461 disequilibrium does not seem to be the reason.

462

463 Table 6. True and estimated $r(\alpha^b, \alpha^{b'})$ across populations 1 and 2, generation 5

	True $r(\alpha^b, \alpha^{b'})$	Estimated $r(\alpha^b, \alpha^{b'})$ with markers	Estimated $r(\alpha^b, \alpha^{b'})$ with QTL
Complete	0.981	0.945	0.970
Dominance			
Complementary	0.933	0.842	0.854
Epistasis			
Additive by additive	0.76	0.60	0.532

464

465 Table 7. True and estimated $r(\alpha^b, \alpha^{b'})$ across generations 1 and 5, population 1

	True $r(\alpha^b, \alpha^{b'})$	Estimated $r(\alpha^b, \alpha^{b'})$ with markers	Estimated $r(\alpha^b, \alpha^{b'})$ with QTL
Complete	0.993	0.976	0.989
Dominance			
Complementary	0.975	0.926	0.943
Epistasis			
Additive by additive	0.899	0.777	0.780

466

467

468

469

DISCUSSION

470

471 The fact that most genetic variation is statistically additive is well known. However, this does
472 not imply equality of statistical additive effects across populations, something that is possibly
473 reflected in the difficulty of predicting across (distinct) populations, either in animal or
474 human genetics. Only recently the role of non-additive biological gene actions in this
475 difficulty has started to be recognized (Dai *et al.* 2020; Duenk *et al.* 2020). Here we confirm
476 and reinforce their findings. These authors presented result of simulations, where the
477 problem is that the results are scenario specific and do not allow a good appraisal of the
478 different factors.

479

480 In this work, we present a general, formal framework that does not depend on specific
481 hypothesis on gene action or order of the epistatic interactions. In our derivation, we
482 approached *high-order functional* epistasis by Taylor expansions, leading to expressions that
483 involve only *low-order statistical* additive epistasis (actually pairwise). Including one extra
484 term in our Taylor expansion would include *three-loci statistical* epistasis and so on, but extra
485 terms would lead to more difficult expressions (covariance of allele frequencies across loci
486 and populations), and it is expected that the magnitude of the statistical effects is smaller
487 and smaller with higher orders of interactions (Mäki-Tanila and Hill 2014). We find
488 reasonable agreement with our simulation and values from literature. However, we have
489 indeed not thoroughly studied by simulation the quality of our approximation, which would
490 require considerable thinking on how to simulate epistasis in very general manners.

491

492 Three main factors influence the correlation of substitution effects between
 493 populations $r(\alpha^b, \alpha^{b'})$: the genetic similarity of the two populations, the extend of additive,
 494 dominance and additive by additive variance, and the distribution of allele frequencies at
 495 QTL. We consider that showing explicitly these three factors is an achievement, as their role
 496 is clear from previous work in simulated and real data, (Martin *et al.* 2019; Dai *et al.* 2020;
 497 Duenk *et al.* 2020). Now we discuss these three factors.

498

499 The distance across populations is conveniently summarized by relationships γ , which
 500 describe covariances of allelic frequencies across populations, and are related to F_{st} indexes.
 501 On ideal populations, these γ relationships depend on the divergence time t but also on the
 502 effective population size N , as shown by the expression $\frac{\gamma_{b,b'}}{8} = Cov(p^b, p^{b'}) \approx 1 -$
 503 $exp(-t/2N)$ (Bonhomme *et al.* 2010). In equation (4), to estimate $r(\alpha^b, \alpha^{b'})$, relationship
 504 enters into the form $(\gamma_{b'} + \gamma_b - 2\gamma_{b,b'})$ which as explained is proportional to the F_{st} index.
 505 If the relationship across populations is very small, $\gamma_{b,b'} = 0$ which results in $(\gamma_{b'} + \gamma_b -$
 506 $2\gamma_{b,b'})$ bounded between 0 (all allele frequencies are 0.5) and 4 (alleles are fixed). The more
 507 diverse each of the populations $(\gamma_{b'}, \gamma_b)$, and the more similar one to the other, the higher
 508 $r(\alpha^b, \alpha^{b'})$ will be.

509

510 The factors $\frac{1}{2} \frac{\bar{H}}{H^2}$ and $\frac{2}{\bar{H}}$ are weighting factors on dominance and additive by additive
 511 variances. If the allele frequencies are modelled using symmetric $Beta(a, a)$ distributions
 512 (see Appendix), these become $\frac{1}{2} \frac{\bar{H}}{H^2} = \frac{1}{4 \frac{a+1}{a} \left(1 + \frac{a+2}{2a+2} \left(\frac{a+3}{2a+3} - 2\right)\right)}$ and $\frac{2}{\bar{H}} = 1 + \frac{1}{2a}$. The first is
 513 bounded between 1.5 (for U-shaped distributions) and 1 (for peaked distributions), so that

514 dominance variation does not play a big role in the difference between substitution effects
515 across populations unless dominance variation is way much larger than additive variation,
516 something that seems unlikely based on theory and estimates. However, the second weight,
517 due to epistasis, is not bounded and is large for small values of a (e.g. 13.5 for
518 $\text{Beta}(0.04,0.04)$), which reflects that functional epistasis plays a strong role in additive
519 variation for U-shaped distributions (Hill *et al.* 2008). This result also reinforces the findings
520 of Duenk *et al.* (2020) and Dai *et al.* (2020) that it is mainly biological epistasis that generates
521 changes in additive substitution effects across populations. For instance, when one
522 population drifts, the additive by additive statistical variation enters into additive variation
523 (Hill *et al.* 2006; Walsh and Lynch 2018).

524

525 Thus, $r(\alpha_i^b, \alpha_i^{b'})$ will be very low only if (1) populations are distinct, (2) there is *statistical*
526 epistatic variation and (3) QTL distributions are U-shaped.

527

528 In most conceivable cases σ_{AA}^2 and σ_D^2 are of magnitudes roughly similar to additive variances
529 (Fuerst and Sölkner 1994; Palucci *et al.* 2007; Hill *et al.* 2008; Mäki-Tanila and Hill 2014;
530 Vitezica *et al.* 2018), and relationships across populations are moderate. Then, for
531 reasonable assumptions about allele distribution of QTLs, we have shown that the
532 correlation of substitution effects across populations is typically around 0.6, which basically
533 agrees with scarce estimates of genetic correlations across populations available in the
534 literature. Our results seem rather robust to different distributions of allele frequencies.
535 These values are low enough so that, for practical purposes, predictions across populations
536 are of little interest, moreover if populations are not closely related as is often the case. This
537 is of practical relevance, e.g. for genomic predictions in livestock improvement, but also in

538 human genetics *e.g.* for the use of European-based Polygenic Risk Scores in individuals from
539 other ancestries (Martin *et al.* 2019)

540

541 Similar results apply to the same populations across generations, in which case the
542 correlation of substitution effects across generations goes from 0.99 (next 1-2 generations)
543 to 0.70 (5-10 generations). This illustrates that, even if genomic predictions would use QTLs
544 or markers in tight LD with QTLs, there would still be a need for a continuous system of
545 data collecting and re-estimation of effects.

546

547

548 In the simulations we confirmed that our estimates are reasonably good although slightly
549 biased downwards. Still, we find that, for the challenging forms of non-additive gene action
550 that we simulated, the results are quite good. For instance, an explicit functional value was
551 only included in the case of complete dominance. The additive by additive epistasis is highly
552 extreme (*e.g.* substitution effects change sign across spectra of allelic frequency). The other
553 form of epistasis, complementary epistasis, has genotypic value depending on every locus
554 being at a particular homozygous genotype and is deemed to be a biological mechanism that
555 contributes to variance stabilization (Mackay 2014). Complementary epistasis generates
556 more additive variation than additive by additive epistasis and, as expected, it leads to higher
557 similarity of substitution effects across populations.

558

559 Another result of our theory is that it allows, at least in principle, to assess if genetic
560 correlation across breeds is due to gene-by-environment or gene-by-gene interaction,
561 without going to a fully parametric analysis. For instance, Legarra *et al.* (2014) estimated a

562 genetic correlation of 0.5 for Latxa Cara Rubia - Manech Tête Rouse, two breeds that have
563 frequent exchanges and are almost identical (in this case, $\Gamma = \begin{pmatrix} \gamma_b & \gamma_{b,b'} \\ \gamma_{b,b'} & \gamma_{b'} \end{pmatrix} =$
564 $\begin{pmatrix} 0.49 & 0.47 \\ 0.47 & 0.51 \end{pmatrix}$). This would result in a value of $r(\alpha^b, \alpha^{b'})$ much higher than 0.5. A possibility
565 is that the low value of 0.5 is due to GxE interaction, as the production systems may differ.
566 This opens new perspectives.

567

568 CONCLUSIONS

569

570 We presented a coherent, approximate theory, that does not invoke any particular
571 mechanism of gene action, to explain and appraise the change in magnitude of (additive)
572 QTL substitution effects across populations and generations. The theory gives good
573 approximate estimates of this correlation, that needs to be otherwise explicitly estimated.
574 More importantly, the theory shows that the main sources for the change of effects are
575 relationships across populations, magnitudes of additive and first-order non-additive
576 variances (dominance and additive by additive), and spectra of allele frequencies. These
577 findings provide better understanding of the properties of genomic prediction methods and
578 of quantitative genetics in general.

579

580

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592 REFERENCES

593

594 Aiello D., K. Patel, and E. Lasagna, 2018 The myostatin gene: an overview of mechanisms of
595 action and its relevance to livestock animals. *Anim. Genet.* 49: 505–519.

596 <https://doi.org/10.1111/age.12696>

597 Baloche G., A. Legarra, G. Sallé, H. Larroque, J. M. Astruc, *et al.*, 2014 Assessment of accuracy
598 of genomic prediction for French Lacaune dairy sheep. *J. Dairy Sci.* 97: 1107–1116.

599 Bonhomme M., C. Chevalet, B. Servin, S. Boitard, J. Abdallah, *et al.*, 2010 Detecting Selection
600 in Population Trees: The Lewontin and Krakauer Test Extended. *Genetics* 186: 241–
601 262. <https://doi.org/10.1534/genetics.110.117275>

602 Bonifati V., P. Rizzu, M. J. van Baren, O. Schaap, G. J. Breedveld, *et al.*, 2003 Mutations in the
603 DJ-1 Gene Associated with Autosomal Recessive Early-Onset Parkinsonism. *Science*
604 299: 256–259. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.1077209>

605 Caballero A., and M. A. Toro, 2002 Analysis of genetic diversity for the management of
606 conserved subdivided populations. *Conserv. Genet.* 3: 289.

607 Caballero A., 2020 *Quantitative Genetics*. Cambridge University Press.

608 Campos G. de los, D. A. Sorensen, and M. A. Toro, 2019 Imperfect Linkage Disequilibrium
609 Generates Phantom Epistasis (& Perils of Big Data). *G3 Genes Genomes Genet.*
610 9: 1429–1436. <https://doi.org/10.1534/g3.119.400101>

611 Carlborg Ö., L. Jacobsson, P. Åhgren, P. Siegel, and L. Andersson, 2006 Epistasis and the
612 release of genetic variation during long-term selection. *Nat. Genet.* 38: 418–420.
613 <https://doi.org/10.1038/ng1761>

614 Dai Z., N. Long, and W. Huang, 2020 Influence of Genetic Interactions on Polygenic
615 Prediction. *G3 Genes Genomes Genet.* 10: 109–115.
616 <https://doi.org/10.1534/g3.119.400812>

617 Duenk P., P. Bijma, M. P. L. Calus, Y. C. J. Wientjes, and J. H. J. van der Werf, 2020 The Impact
618 of Non-additive Effects on the Genetic Correlation Between Populations. *G3 Genes
619 Genomes Genet.* 10: 783–795. <https://doi.org/10.1534/g3.119.400663>

620 Fernandez E. N., J.P. Sanchez, R. Martinez, A. Legarra, M. Baselga, 2017 Role of inbreeding
621 depression, non-inbred dominance deviations and random year-season effect in
622 genetic trends for prolificacy in rabbit closed lines. *J. Anim. Breed. Genet.* 6: 441–452.

623 Falconer D. S., and T. F. C. Mackay, 1996 *Introduction to quantitative genetics*. Longman New
624 York.

625 Fuerst C., and J. Sölkner, 1994 Additive and Nonadditive Genetic Variances for Milk Yield,
626 Fertility, and Lifetime Performance Traits of Dairy Cattle. *J. Dairy Sci.* 77: 1114–1125.
627 [https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.S0022-0302\(94\)77047-8](https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.S0022-0302(94)77047-8)

628 Fuerst C., J. W. James, J. Sölkner, and A. Essl, 1997 Impact of dominance and epistasis on the
629 genetic make-up of simulated populations under selection: a model development. J.
630 Anim. Breed. Genet. 114: 163–175. [https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1439-](https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1439-0388.1997.tb00502.x)
631 0388.1997.tb00502.x

632 Garcia-Baccino C. A., A. Legarra, O. F. Christensen, I. Misztal, I. Pocrnic, *et al.*, 2017
633 Metafounders are related to Fst fixation indices and reduce bias in single-step
634 genomic evaluations. Genet. Sel. Evol. 49: 34. [https://doi.org/10.1186/s12711-017-](https://doi.org/10.1186/s12711-017-0309-2)
635 0309-2

636 García-Ruiz A., J. B. Cole, P. M. VanRaden, G. R. Wiggans, F. J. Ruiz-López, *et al.*, 2016
637 Changes in genetic selection differentials and generation intervals in US Holstein
638 dairy cattle as a result of genomic selection. Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. 113: E3995–E4004.

639 Gautier M., A. Capitan, S. Fritz, A. Eggen, D. Boichard, *et al.*, 2007 Characterization of the
640 DGAT1 K232A and Variable Number of Tandem Repeat Polymorphisms in French
641 Dairy Cattle. J. Dairy Sci. 90: 2980–2988. <https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.2006-707>

642 Grobet L., L. J. Royo Martin, D. Poncelet, D. Pirottin, B. Brouwers, *et al.*, 1997 A deletion in
643 the bovine myostatin gene causes the double-muscling phenotype in cattle. Nat.
644 Genet. 17: 71–74. <https://doi.org/10.1038/ng0997-71>

645 Haile-Mariam M., and J. E. Pryce, 2015 Variances and correlations of milk production,
646 fertility, longevity, and type traits over time in Australian Holstein cattle. J. Dairy Sci.
647 98: 7364–7379. <https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.2015-9537>

648 Hayes B. J., P. J. Bowman, A. C. Chamberlain, K. Verbyla, and M. E. Goddard, 2009 Accuracy
649 of genomic breeding values in multi-breed dairy cattle populations. *Genet Sel Evol*
650 41: 51.

651 Hill W. G., N. H. Barton, and M. Turelli, 2006 Prediction of effects of genetic drift on variance
652 components under a general model of epistasis. *Theor. Popul. Biol.* 70: 56–62.
653 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tpb.2005.10.001>

654 Hill W. G., M. E. Goddard, and P. M. Visscher, 2008 Data and Theory Point to Mainly Additive
655 Genetic Variance for Complex Traits. *PLOS Genet.* 4: e1000008.
656 <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pgen.1000008>

657 Karoui S., M. J. Carabaño, C. Díaz, and A. Legarra, 2012 Joint genomic evaluation of French
658 dairy cattle breeds using multiple-trait models. *Genet Sel Evol* 44: 39.

659 Kojima K., 1959 Role of epistasis and overdominance in stability of equilibria with selection.
660 *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.* 45: 984–989.

661 Kojima K.-I., 1961 Effects of dominance and size of population on response to mass
662 selection*. *Genet. Res.* 2: 177–188. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S0016672300000689>

663 Lande R., and R. Thompson, 1990 Efficiency of marker-assisted selection in the improvement
664 of quantitative traits. *Genetics* 124: 743–756.

665 Legarra A., G. Baloche, F. Barillet, J.-M. Astruc, C. Soulas, *et al.*, 2014 Within-and across-
666 breed genomic predictions and genomic relationships for Western Pyrenees dairy
667 sheep breeds Latxa, Manech, and Basco-Béarnaise. *J. Dairy Sci.* 97: 3200–3212.

668 Legarra A., O. F. Christensen, Z. G. Vitezica, I. Aguilar, and I. Misztal, 2015 Ancestral
669 Relationships Using Metafounders: Finite Ancestral Populations and Across
670 Population Relationships. *Genetics* 200: 455–468.
671 <https://doi.org/10.1534/genetics.115.177014>

672 Lewontin R. C., and J. Krakauer, 1973 Distribution of Gene Frequency as a Test of the Theory
673 of the Selective Neutrality of Polymorphisms. *Genetics* 74: 175–195.

674 Liu Z., H. Alkholder, F. Reinhardt, and R. Reents, 2016 Accuracy and bias of genomic
675 prediction for second-generation candidates. *Interbull Bull.* 50: 17-23.

676 Lynch M., and B. Walsh, 1998 *Genetics and analysis of quantitative traits*. Sinauer associates.

677 Mackay T. F. C., 2014 Epistasis and Quantitative Traits: Using Model Organisms to Study
678 Gene-Gene Interactions. *Nat. Rev. Genet.* 15: 22–33.
679 <https://doi.org/10.1038/nrg3627>

680 Mackay T. F. C., 2015 Epistasis for Quantitative Traits in *Drosophila*, pp. 47–70 in *Epistasis:*
681 *Methods and Protocols*, *Methods in Molecular Biology*. edited by Moore J. H.,
682 Williams S. M. Springer, New York, NY.

683 MacLeod I. M., P. J. Bowman, C. J. Vander Jagt, M. Haile-Mariam, K. E. Kemper, *et al.*, 2016
684 Exploiting biological priors and sequence variants enhances QTL discovery and
685 genomic prediction of complex traits. *BMC Genomics* 17: 144.
686 <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12864-016-2443-6>

687 Magwire M. M., A. Yamamoto, M. A. Carbone, N. V. Roshina, A. V. Symonenko, *et al.*, 2010
688 Quantitative and Molecular Genetic Analyses of Mutations Increasing *Drosophila* Life
689 Span. PLOS Genet. 6: e1001037. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pgen.1001037>

690 Mäki-Tanila A., and W. G. Hill, 2014 Influence of Gene Interaction on Complex Trait Variation
691 with Multilocus Models. Genetics 198: 355–367.
692 <https://doi.org/10.1534/genetics.114.165282>

693 Martin A. R., M. Kanai, Y. Kamatani, Y. Okada, B. M. Neale, *et al.*, 2019 Clinical use of current
694 polygenic risk scores may exacerbate health disparities. Nat. Genet. 51: 584–591.
695 <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41588-019-0379-x>

696 Meuwissen T. H. E., B. J. Hayes, and M. E. Goddard, 2001 Prediction of total genetic value
697 using genome-wide dense marker maps. Genetics 157: 1819–1829.

698 Moghaddar N., M. Khansefid, J. H. J. van der Werf, S. Bolormaa, N. Duijvesteijn, *et al.*, 2019
699 Genomic prediction based on selected variants from imputed whole-genome
700 sequence data in Australian sheep populations. Genet. Sel. Evol. 51: 72.
701 <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12711-019-0514-2>

702 Palucci V., L. R. Schaeffer, F. Miglior, and V. Osborne, 2007 Non-additive genetic effects for
703 fertility traits in Canadian Holstein cattle (Open Access publication). Genet. Sel. Evol.
704 39: 181. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1297-9686-39-2-181>

705 Porto-Neto L. R., W. Barendse, J. M. Henshall, S. M. McWilliam, S. A. Lehnert, *et al.*, 2015
706 Genomic correlation: harnessing the benefit of combining two unrelated populations

707 for genomic selection. *Genet. Sel. Evol.* 47: 84. [https://doi.org/10.1186/s12711-015-](https://doi.org/10.1186/s12711-015-0162-0)
708 0162-0

709 Robertson A., 1975 Gene Frequency Distributions as a Test of Selective Neutrality. *Genetics*
710 81: 775–785.

711 Rodríguez-Ramilo S., J. M. Elsen, and A. Legarra, 2019 Inbreeding and effective population
712 size in French dairy sheep: Comparison between genomic and pedigree estimates. *J.*
713 *Dairy Sci.* 102: 4227–4237.

714 Roos A. P. W. de, B. J. Hayes, and M. E. Goddard, 2009 Reliability of Genomic Predictions
715 Across Multiple Populations. *Genetics* 183: 1545–1553.
716 <https://doi.org/10.1534/genetics.109.104935>

717 Rupp R., P. Senin, J. Sarry, C. Allain, C. Tasca, *et al.*, 2015 A Point Mutation in Suppressor of
718 Cytokine Signalling 2 (Socs2) Increases the Susceptibility to Inflammation of the
719 Mammary Gland while Associated with Higher Body Weight and Size and Higher Milk
720 Production in a Sheep Model. *PLOS Genet.* 11: e1005629.
721 <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pgen.1005629>

722 Searle S., 1971 *Linear models*. New York, NY (EUA). John Wiley.

723 Streit M., N. Neugebauer, T. H. E. Meuwissen, and J. Bennewitz, 2011 Short communication:
724 evidence for a major gene by polygene interaction for milk production traits in
725 German Holstein dairy cattle. *J. Dairy Sci.* 94: 1597–1600.
726 <https://doi.org/10.3168/jds.2010-3834>

727 Tsuruta S., I. Misztal, T. J. Lawlor, and L. Klei, 2004 Modeling final scores in US Holsteins as a
728 function of year of classification using a random regression model. *Livest. Prod. Sci.*
729 91: 199–207. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.livprodsci.2003.09.016>

730 VanRaden P., K. Olson, G. Wiggans, J. Cole, and M. Tooker, 2011 Genomic inbreeding and
731 relationships among Holsteins, Jerseys, and Brown Swiss. *J. Dairy Sci.* 94: 5673–5682.

732 Vitezica Z. G., A. Reverter, W. Herring, and A. Legarra, 2018 Dominance and epistatic genetic
733 variances for litter size in pigs using genomic models. *Genet. Sel. Evol.* 50: 1–8.

734 Walsh B., and M. Lynch, 2018 *Evolution and Selection of Quantitative Traits*. Oxford
735 University Press.

736 Welsh C. S., T. S. Stewart, C. Schwab, and H. D. Blackburn, 2010 Pedigree analysis of 5 swine
737 breeds in the United States and the implications for genetic conservation. *J. Anim.*
738 *Sci.* 88: 1610–1618. <https://doi.org/10.2527/jas.2009-2537>

739 Wientjes Y. C. J., P. Bijma, J. Vandenplas, and M. P. L. Calus, 2017 Multi-population Genomic
740 Relationships for Estimating Current Genetic Variances Within and Genetic
741 Correlations Between Populations. *Genetics* 207: 503–515.
742 <https://doi.org/10.1534/genetics.117.300152>

743 Wolc A., J. Arango, P. Settar, J. E. Fulton, N. P. O’Sullivan, *et al.*, 2011 Persistence of accuracy
744 of genomic estimated breeding values over generations in layer chickens. *Genet Sel*
745 *Evol* 43: 23.

746 Xiang T., B. Nielsen, G. Su, A. Legarra, and O. F. Christensen, 2016 Application of single-step
747 genomic evaluation for crossbred performance in pig. *J. Anim. Sci.* 94: 936–948.
748 <https://doi.org/10.2527/jas.2015-9930>

749 Xiang T., O. F. Christensen, and A. Legarra, 2017 Technical note: Genomic evaluation for
750 crossbred performance in a single-step approach with metafounders. *J. Anim. Sci.* 95:
751 1472–1480.

752

753

754